

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Psychology

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Developing the Instructions for the Controlled Association Experiment by Means of Semantic Features for the Stimulus “Flirting Person”

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

This article continues a series of studies devoted to ludic competence/playfulness and one of its components is flirting.

The aim of the study: in the context of parametric concept of meaning, to identify on the basis of applied psycholinguistic research the semantic components of the stimulus “flirting person”, which are actualized in the speech acts of Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine.

Material and Methods:

The main method of the research is a psycholinguistic experiment whose major stage is the controlled association experiment with the stimulus “flirting person”. The sample comprised 215 young people (aged 21-35), of which 112 females and 103 males.

Results:

At the final stage of formulation of the instructions 23 semantic features were selected for the stimulus “flirting person”. The results of the controlled association experiment with the stimulus “flirting person” allowed to build 23 associative fields and obtain the material for describing the behaviour pattern of ludic position Diplomat (flirting person) reflecting the reality of linguistic consciousness of young Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine.

Conclusions:

Cluster analysis of the associative field of the semantic feature “What is the person’s marital status?” allowed to define: three core clusters – “Free” (71.16%), “In a relationship” (14.42%), “Any” (3.72%); three peripheral clusters – “Qualities” (3.26%), “Emotional State” (3.26)%, “Role in family relations” (1.40%); extreme peripheral clusters – “Changeable” (0.93%); an isolated female reaction “Guy” suggests an ambiguous interpretation and allows to highlight different meanings – “Gender” and “Age”.

Keywords:

ludic competence, playfulness, ludic position, flirting person, psycholinguistic experiment, controlled association experiment, youth

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Introduction

This article continues a series of studies devoted to ludic competence/playfulness and one of its components is flirting (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a).

We define ludic competence as a system of inner resources to which a person turns (in the context of conflict/difficult interpersonal interaction) in order to balance their personality against external conditions of the social environment on the basis of positive emotions, interest and joy, which are frequently expressed affectively and accompanied by tension and excitement. By inner resources we understand playfulness, an integral stable personality trait.

Playfulness as a stable personality trait has been studied by the scientists since 1975 (Barnett, 1990; Bowman, 1987; Bundy, 1996; Chapman, 1978; Csikszentmihalyi, 1975; Groos, 1976; Guitard et al., 2005; Proyer, 2012; 2017; Proyer & Jehle, 2013; Qian & Yarnal, 2011; Schaefer & Greenberg, 1997; Shen, 2010; Yue et al., 2016) covering person's system of personality resources, adaptational potential, etc. and first of all it is associated in general with mental well-being; coping strategies; social intelligence and in particular with "virtual type of communicative competence" (Kobzieva, 2020, p. 38).

We determine playfulness as an integral stable personality trait, which shows as the individual creative adaptation to the reality of their own "Self" (individual identity) and to the reality of the "Other" (social identity): every conflict/difficult situation can be faced as a challenge rather than a threat. This definition of playfulness is close to the concept of Guitard et al. (2005, p. 19). From this point on the "Other" is understood as a subject/subjects of conflict/difficult interpersonal interaction.

The research of playfulness is carried out by means of psycholinguistic instruments.

The principal stage of the psycholinguistic experiment included a longitudinal free association test with the stimulus "playfulness" on the sample of 4,795 respondents that allowed to verify the components of playfulness and corresponding ludic positions: "sensitivity" (sensitive) – "Empath"; "humour" (funny) – "Real humourist"; "ease" (easy) – "balance-master"; "imagination" (imaginative) – "Sculptor"; "flirting" (flirtatious) – "Diplomat"; "impishness" (impish) – "Frolicsome fellow"; "fugue" (fugue) – "Holy fool" (Gordienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018; Kobzieva et al., 2019).

The components of playfulness/ ludic competence are defined as "self-motivated abilities" (Raven, 2001), which allow people to achieve personally significant goals. In terms of our concept such goal is efficient management of conflicts/problems in the context of interpersonal interaction (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a).

As it is shown above, each of seven "self-motivated abilities" has a corresponding ludic position. The names of ludic positions are justified both theoretically and empirically (Gordienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018; Kobzieva et al., 2019) and were tested

during coaching sessions in ludic competence, which are part of the curriculum of psychology students in H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University. Ludic position is a way how individual creative adaptation to the reality of their own "Self" and to the reality of the "Other". Ludic position reflects the experience of displaying playfulness/ludic competence in various standard and non-standard situations, i.e. a behavioral aspect. Thus, acquiring the ludic positions implies acquiring behavior patterns.

Within our research we are especially interested in the studies where a close relationship of flirting and playfulness is shown.

Playfulness is a subject of active research as a highly desirable trait in potential long-term mates (Chick et al., 2012; Fredrickson, 2003; Gordienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018; Kobzieva et al., 2019; J. Lauer & Lauer, 2002; Proyer & Wagner, 2015; Weber & Ruch, 2012) starting with the studies of Woll (1989), where playfulness is associated with different styles of sexual behavior, certain types of affection and love:

- playfulness as a spontaneous, idiosyncratic "private game" plays a definite part in establishing positive relationships and settling conflicts and, more broadly, tends to stabilize family relationship (Betcher, 1981);
- playfulness as an important trait of potential partners for romantic relationship (J. Lauer & Lauer, 2002; Fredrickson, 2003; Weber & Ruch, 2012);
- playfulness is an evolutionarily significant characteristic when choosing a sexual partner as "a highly desirable trait in long-term sexual mates" (Chick et al., 2012; Proyer & Wagner, 2015).

Certainly, we also considered the studies where flirting was the subject of research without any connection with playfulness. As a psychological phenomenon flirting and its certain aspects are covered in the works of Bern (2017) as a kind of light game, which implies presence of a double secret interaction of ego states and in the works of Gangestad (cited by Rodgers, 1999), as a negotiation process that takes place after an initial contribution. Hall (2013) identified 5 styles of flirting; Henningsen et al. (2008) determined 6 motives of flirting; Watzlawick (1983) defined 30 steps of flirting "from the first eye contact to sex"; Givens (1978, p. 346–359) and Whitty (2003, p. 343–344) described non-verbal cues for flirting.

Based on theoretical and empirical studies of the scientists mentioned above, the results of psycholinguistic studies, flirting as an individual scale of ludic competence/playfulness was singled out in the structure of ludic competence questionnaire (LCQ) developed in terms of psycholinguistics by domestic psychologists Kobzieva et al. (2019).

In the frame of our ludic competence coaching sessions we consider flirting as the ability to take attention and get on the right side of somebody of the same or the opposite gender through verbal and non-verbal communication in order to establish and maintain mutually beneficial relationships based on the feeling of emotional bond; "to promote" Other in the desired

direction (Kobzieva et al., 2019).

In our ludic competence coaching sessions describing the behaviour pattern of a ludic position rest upon its psychological and psycholinguistic structure. Identifying the specific psycholinguistic structure implies carrying out psycholinguistic experiments. The results of the psycholinguistic experiment allow to consider: gender-specific differences in the perception of the stimulus flirting, emotional and evaluative attitude to it, relevant meanings of flirting for the linguistic consciousness of the Russian-speaking population of Ukraine, etc. The psycholinguistic study of concept flirting conducted by Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., (2021a) made it possible to broaden both its meaning due to the semantic components actualized in speech acts and partly the behaviour pattern of the corresponding ludic position – Diplomat (Kobzieva et al., 2019).

We “describe” this behaviour pattern of the ludic position Diplomat in the context of parametric concept of the meaning for the first time.

Inventory of semantic features of lexemes of the language is a relevant psycholinguistic problem.

The aim of the study. In the context of parametric concept of meaning, to identify on the basis of applied psycholinguistic research the semantic components of the stimulus “flirting person”, which are actualized in the speech acts of Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine.

In accordance with the purpose the following research tasks were determined:

- to develop instructions for a controlled association experiment (CAE) based on the semantic features relevant to the semantics of “flirting person”;
- to present the main strategies and methods of distributing the obtained associates for the semantic features into the semantic clusters.

Materials and Methods

The method of the conducted research was a psycholinguistic experiment, whose main stage was the CAE with the stimulus “flirting person”. Additional methods included a survey (to clarify the results of the CAE), questionnaires (to clarify the characteristics of the sample). Frequency and cluster analysis were used as mathematical and statistical methods for analyzing the research results, which made it possible to identify trends in distribution of associations in the experimental group.

The CAE with the stimulus “flirting person” was carried out in writing. According to the instructions, the respondents should indicate gender, age, education/specialty, marital status and write the first word that comes into mind when answering each question (semantic feature).

The total number of respondents who took part in the experiment was 215 young people (age 21-35), 112 females and 103 males. “By education”: 44% – were undergraduates, 35% – had a university degree, 9% – completed secondary school; “by marital status”: 60% – were in a marriage-like relationship (unregistered

marriage), 13% – are in a registered civil marriage, 27% – are not in a relationship.

CAE allows to focus on the peripheral components and evaluativity of the stimulus word in question, while the free experiment foregrounds the brightest components of meaning. When formulating the instructions for the CAE in terms of the parametric concept of Sternin (2011), we firstly identified the main semantic features of the sense class of lexis to which our stimulus “flirting person” belongs.

The parametric concept of meaning assumes that the meaning is built from certain semantic features and different semantic types of lexis should have different set of these features. Defining the semantic features for a psycholinguistic experiment with certain semantic classes of lexis requires special research. Therefore, we used the semantics of the names of persons with semantic features described in the work of Sternin “Psycholinguistic meaning of a word and its description” (Sternin, 2011, p. 132–139), for example: the bearer of the feature, appearance, age, experience, etc.

The principal semantic parameters relevant to communication were obtained in the course of describing the meanings of Russian nouns in Sternin’s work “The lexical meaning of word in speech” (Sternin, 1985).

For the sake of convenience, all semantic features are given within the framework of the corresponding semantic aspects (for example, biological aspect, temporal aspect, social and cultural aspect, etc.). As for emic specifiers, they are given along with the corresponding semantic features if this feature is closed. If the feature is open, semantic specifiers are not given, since in this case their number is unlimited (Sternin, 2011, p. 135). For example, such a semantic aspect as biological (aspect) includes four semantic features: 1) demand for food: high, low; 2) biological state; 3) attitude to the opposite gender; 4) health: healthy, unhealthy. In the biological aspect we have selected the second and third semantic features. We give in brackets a number of a semantic feature according to Sternin’s classification (Sternin, 2011, p. 135) and a semantic feature we that have added is given with number and asterisk. The question itself is highlighted in capital letters, as it is given in the instructions; the number of the question corresponds to the number in the instruction, which is be given below.

Biological aspect:

2. What is the person’s gender? (biological gender: male, female).

13. What is the person’s attitude to the opposite gender? (attitude to the opposite gender).

14. What is the person’s attitude to the same gender? (attitude to the same gender).

Thus, depending on the semantics of a particular word, suitable semantic features are selected for posing a question and formulating the instructions.

At the initial stage the formulation procedure for the instructions for the CAE with the stimulus “flirting person” also implied systematization and generalization

of the outcomes of theoretical and empirical psychological studies devoted to the phenomenon of “flirting”; systematization and generalization of the results of psycholinguistic research devoted to the concept of “flirting”.

Results

We have formulated 28 questions (semantic features). The 28-question instructions passed approbation on a sample of 115 respondents (age 21-35). Based on the results of the analysis of the obtained associative fields, at the intermediary stage 26 questions were left. At the final stage of the study, 23 semantic features were selected; they were recognized as relevant for the stimulus flirting person and allowed to obtain the material reflecting the reality of linguistic consciousness of native speakers in order to describe the behaviour pattern of the ludic position Diplomat (flirting person). In the Table A only those questions-semantic features (first column), which reflect best the content of the behaviour pattern of the ludic position Diplomat, are given. The semantic feature numbering in the table corresponds to their numbering in our questionnaire. Semantic features did not include in Table A:

5. What is the state of the person’s finances?
6. What social class does the person belong to?
9. What is the person’s moral stature?
14. What is the person’s attitude to the same gender?
19. What is the person’s behavior?
21. What is the person’s motive?
23. What is your overall assessment of the person?

In the course of building an associative field for each semantic feature, the frequencies of reactions are calculated, and the frequencies of all reactions indicated by the corresponding number are presented in descending order. If the frequencies are equal, the responses go in alphabetical order. The number of respondents who declined to answer is indicated at the end of a built associative field. The reactions (words with an asterisk) in the presented associative fields (second column) in the original research correspond to the feminine Russian words.

The outcome of the study assumes distribution of 215 reactions across semantic clusters for each of the 23 semantic features. In one of our studies, the semantic feature “What is the person’s motive?” (Gordienko-Mitrofanova et al., 2021b) was considered. In this work we consider another one of 23 semantic features of the word combination “flirting person” – “What is the person’s marital status?” The association reactions obtained for this semantic parameter on the sample of 215 respondents (112 women and 103 men) are as follows: 40 unique reactions, including 4-word combinations, 19 reactions with a frequency greater than one, 21 isolated reactions, 0 declined to answer the question.

215 reactions were grouped into the following clusters (semantic groups):

1. “Free”: free (50), single (28), not married (23), bachelor (17), not in a relationship (11), single* (10), actively in quest (3), none (3), widower (2), not married* (2), nobody (2), empty (2); total 153 (71.16%), of which female 73 (33.95%), male 80 (37.21%).

2. “In a relationship”: total 31 (14.42%), of which female 21 (9.77%), male 10 (4.65%).

This cluster consists of two sub-clusters:

2.1 “Registered relationship (marriage)”: married (10), married* (8); total 18 (8.37%), of which female 14 (6.51%), male 4 (1.86%).

2.2 “Unregistered relationship”: in a relationship (10), goes out with somebody (1), busy (1); at the initial stage of romantic relationships (1); total 13 (6.05%), of which female 7 (3.26%), male 6 (2.79%).

3. “Any”: any (4), it doesn’t matter (4); total 8 (3.72%), of which female 5 (2.32%), male 3 (1.40%).

4. “Qualities”: kind (1), caring* (1), reliable* (1), responsible* (1), open (1), positive (1), family man (1); total 7 (3.26%), of which female 4 (1.86%), male 3 (1.40%).

5. “Emotional state”: happy (3), in love (2), beloved* (1), amorous (1); total 7 (3.26%), of which female 2 (0.93%), male 5 (2.33%).

6. “Role in family relations”: chief (1), equal (1), average (1); total 3 (1.40%), of which female 2 (0.93%), male 1 (0.47%).

7. “Changeable”: changeable (1), free (not exactly) (1); total 2 (0.93%), of which female 1 (0.47%), male 1 (0.47%).

8. “Gender”, “Age”: guy 1 (0.47%), female (0.47%).

Uninterpreted reactions are as follows:

1) reactions whose connection with the stimulus “flirting person” is individual and incomprehensible to the researchers: I don’t understand (1), norm (1); total 2 (0.93%), female (0,93%);

2) echo reaction: flirting person 1 (0.47%), female (0.47%).

To make it more obvious, the clusters described above are shown in Figure 1. As can be seen from the diagram, most respondents (71.16%) believe that flirting person is free (“Free”), 14.42% suppose that he can be in a relationship (“In a relationship”), 3.72% of the respondents consider that marital status does not matter (“Any”), 0.93% admit that marital status can change (“Changeable”). Peripheral clusters (less than 10.0%, but more than 1.0%) such as “Qualities” (3.26%), “Emotional state” (3.26%) in terms of scientific philological analysis turn out to be “false” in quotation marks, since nothing is false in the psycholinguistic meaning as well as in the clusters of semantic features. There, all semantic components make the psychological reality (Sternin, 2011, p. 148). The peripheral cluster “Role in family relations” (1.40%) is contamination: it is confused with role in the family. And, finally, the isolated female reaction “guy” suggests an ambiguous interpretation and allows to highlight different meanings – “Gender” and “Age”.

Figure 1
 Results of Cluster Analysis of the Semantic Feature “What is the Person’s Marital Status?”

Figure 2 also reflects gender differences in perception of the question (semantic feature) “What is the person’s marital status?”. Here the nuclear cluster (more than 10%), which we called for our purpose “In a relationship”, draws attention. This cluster is

represented mostly by female reactions (female 10%, male 5%), i. e. women admit that flirting person, regardless of gender, can be in a registered or unregistered relationship.

Figure 2
 Results of Comparative Analysis of Associations of Male and Female Samples of the Semantic Feature “What is the Person’s Marital Status?”

Figure 3 shows the results of cluster analysis of the semantic feature “What is the person’s motive?” described in detail in the study “Flirting person” in the linguistic consciousness of the Russian-speaking

population of Ukraine (based on the results of the controlled association experiment) (Gordienko-Mitrofanova et al., 2021b).

Figure 3
 Results of Cluster Analysis of the Semantic Feature “What is the Person’s Motive?”

Figure 4 demonstrates gender differences in perception of the question (semantic feature) “What is the person’s motive?”. The semantic content of this semantic parameter

depends on gender identification based on the results of the analysis of female and male associative fields. Males are driven by the sexual or indefinite motives, whereas females have social and entertaining ones.

Figure 4

Results of Comparative Analysis of Associations of Male and Female Samples of the Semantic Feature “What is the person’s motive?”

Discussion

We are not aware of any studies in the Ukrainian, Russian and English languages covering the controlled association experiments with the stimulus “flirting person”. This is the basis for the fact that when describing the psycholinguistic structure of the behavior pattern of ludic position Diplomat, we can only rely on free association experiments with the stimulus “flirting” conducted by the domestic scientists (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a; Kobzieva et al., 2020) and Russian scientists (Karaulov et al., 2002), who carried out their studies in the 90s of the twentieth century. At the same time, the latter (the studies of Russian scientists) can only be used in comparative analysis of the semantic components of the word “flirt” that are relevant in speech in different time periods.

At this stage of the study, according to the results of the analysis of the built associative fields for each semantic feature of the stimulus “flirting person”, firstly, we can claim that the method we chose for formulating the instructions for the CAE based on the semantic features of the word semantics, which had been developed by Sternin (1985) in terms of the parametric concept of meaning, is the most adequate for describing behaviour patterns of the ludic positions. This is confirmed by the results of the free association experiment (FAE) with the stimulus “Holy Fool” (Gordiienko-Mytrofanova & Kobzieva, 2018). The results obtained are quite useful for describing the psychological and psycholinguistic structure of a behaviour pattern, but they do not allow to obtain distinctive features of the object under study. By comparison, CAE directly allows to actualize the

behavioral aspect using semantic features and semantic specifiers, for example, in the instructions these are semantic features 6-22.

Secondly, the results of clustering, for example, the semantic feature “What is the person’s motive?”, strongly indicate that the method we have chosen is the most adequate for achieving our target. For example, all six motives of flirting described by Henningsen and his colleagues in the context of theory of cognitive valence theory (sexual, relational, exploring, esteem, instrumental, and fun) (Henningsen et al., 2008) find their confirmation not only in the linguistic consciousness of Russian-speaking residents of Ukraine, but also expand the range of motives, as Figure 3 shows, through the extreme peripheral clusters – “indefinite motive” and “motive of intrinsic motivation”.

The results of clustering the semantic feature “What is the person’s marital status?” presented in this study, indirectly reflect both the empirical data of Henningsen and his colleagues and the five styles of flirting identified by Hall (physical, traditional, sincere, polite, and playful), which were confirmed by the exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses on the big sample of adults (N = 5020) (Hall et al., 2010; Hall, 2013). The clustering data of the given semantic feature are also reflected in the results of the FAE with the stimulus “flirting”, for example, in such clusters as “forms and types of interaction” (25.25%) and “gender” (10.5%) (Gordienko-Mytrofanova et al., 2021a).

On the one hand, the presented semantic features and semantic specifiers certainly reflect not all semantic components but only those which are most often

actualized in the acts of speech. And formulation of these components has a relative nature since all the components of meaning have more than a single description in the metalanguage, and metalanguage variants of description of the same component can take place (Sternin, 2011, p. 139). On the other hand, through formulating the instructions for CAE by means of semantic features with the stimulus “flirting person” we can obtain a large number of associations reflecting various differential features of the object under study.

Conclusions

This study belongs to a number of scientific works devoted to the analysis and description of the concepts of culture and national linguistic pictures of the world. We see the prospect of further research in clustering semantic features defined for the stimulus “flirting person”. This will make it possible to describe the psychological and psycholinguistic structure of the ludic position Diplomat corresponding to such a “self-motivated ability” of playfulness/ludic competence as flirting as a unit of psychological reality of linguistic consciousness of young Russian-speaking inhabitants of Ukraine by means of attraction of a large number of peripheral semantic meanings, as well as semantic components of a linguistic and cultural nature, which cannot be detected by traditional methods of semantic analysis.

Ethical Approval

The authors ensure that the study has been carried out in accordance with The Code of Ethics of the World Medical Association (Declaration of Helsinki) for experiments involving humans; approved by the local institutional review board (protocol No. 12 of the Department of Psychology of H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, 22.03.2021). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

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Table A

Semantic Features for the Stimulus “Flirting Person” and Corresponding Associative Fields

Questions (semantic features)	Associative fields (frequencies of reactions)
1. Who is the person as a carrier of the feature?	Girl (33), person (30), man (26), he (18), guy (17), woman (14), she (13), friend (3), Kirill (3), Casanova (2), coquetry (2), flirtatious person (2), interested person (2), playful (2), Alina Derkach (1), Anton (1), anyone (1), attractive (1), carefree (1), Dima (1), dude (1), everybody (1), explorer (1), female hobgoblin (1), fox (1), fellow student (1), female (1), flirting addict (1), flirt-bearer (1), groupmate* (1), girl with low moral standards (1), girlfriend (1), handsome man (1), hare (1), husband (1), I don't know (1), in love (1), intellectual (1), interesting* (1), interlocutor (1), lion (1), me (1), makes a good impression (1), mademoiselle (1), player (1); party girl (1), pickup artist (1), raccoon (1), she mispronounces “r” or she does it properly (1), seducer (1), swear word (1), tom-cat (1), tempter (1); timid person (1), turtle (1), vamp (1), Vasya (1), wave (1), walking (1), who (1), words (1).
2. What is the person's gender?	Female (104), male (92), doesn't matter (5), wooden (5), any (2), he (2), laminate (2), girl (1), red (1), transgender (1).
3. What is the person's age?	Twenty (33), twenty five (28), twenty three (13), middle (13), young (13), twenty one (8), twenty four (8), eighteen (7), any (6), from twenty to thirty (5), nineteen (4), twenty two (4), doesn't matter (3), from twenty to twenty five (3), sixteen (3), thirty (3), young (3), from eighteen to twenty two (2), from eighteen to thirty (2), from nineteen to twenty five (2), from seventeen to twenty five (2), of age (2), sufficient (2), twenty eight (2), twenty six (2), adult (1), agemate (1), big (1), Balzac's (1), close (1), doesn't matter* (1), from eighteen to twenty (1), from eighteen to twenty one (1), from eighteen to twenty three (1), from eighteen to thirty one (1), from twenty to twenty two (1), from twenty to forty five (1), from twenty to thirty five (1), from twenty one to thirty (1), from twenty five to twenty eight (1), from twenty five to thirty (1), from twenty four to twenty eight (1), from twenty six to thirty one (1), from nineteen to twenty six (1), female (1), from sixteen to twenty six (1), from fifteen to one hundred (1), from fifteen to sixty (1), twenty and up (1), from seventeen to twenty eight (1), forty (1), forty five (1), he (1), junior (1), mature (1), normal (1), older (1), summer (1), small (1), seventeen (1), twenty seven or twenty eight (1), twenty and older in the spring of life (1), thirty two (1), thirty years old (1), thirty five (1), young (1), young - about 20 human years old (1).
4. What is the person's marital status?	Free (50), single (28), not married (23), bachelor (17), not in a relationship (11), in a relationship (10), married (10), single* (10), married* (8), doesn't matter (4), of any status (4), actively in quest (3), happy (3), none (3), empty (2), in love (2), not married* (2), nobody (2), widower (2), amorous (1), average (1), a family man (1), at the initial stage of a romantic relationship (1), beloved* (1), busy (1), caring* (1), changeable (1), chief (1), equal (1), free (not sure) (1), goes out with somebody (1), guy (1), I don't understand (1), kind (1), normal (1), open (1), person who flirts (1), positive (1), responsible* (1), reliable* (1).
7. How intelligent is the person?	Smart (56), high (28), average (27), educated (13), developed (11), above average (8), intellectually savvy (7), erudite (5), any (3), dumb (3), pretty clever (3), quick-witted (3), witty (3), well-read (3), below average (2), clever (2), genius (2), highly intelligent (2), intelligent* (2), narrow-minded (2), not stupid (2), stupid (2), adequate (1), adult (1), animated* (1), boring (1); cunning person (1), doesn't matter (1), free (1), gifted (1), I think there may be variation (1), independent (1), like me but smarter (1), mediocre (1), not very smart (1), normal (1), on a level (1), peculiar (1), personality (1), quick-witted* (1), rational (1), rocky (1); smart enough* (1), sensible (1), to some extent (1), versatile (1), weak (1), wise* (1).
8. How cultured is the person?	Cultured (48), well-conducted (28), educated (26), high (20), middle (13), high level of culture (7), developed (3), polite (3), high culture (3), adequate (2), any (2), common (2), highly cultured (2), intelligent (2), low (2), narrow-minded (2), normal (2), pleasant (2), smart (2), vulgar (2), aristocrat* (1), beautiful (1), creative* (1), confident (1), considerate (1), clinging (1), courteous (1), dependent person (1), diplomatic (1), excellent (1), enlightened (1), erudite (1), good (1), grey* (1), I don't know how to answer (1), in love (1), intellectual (1), illuminated (1), interested* (1), lowbrow (1), literate (1), liberated (1), lacking culture (1), miscellaneous (1), nontypical (1), necessarily cultured (1), not lowbrow (1), peculiar (1), person who flirts (1), posh (1), small (1), spiritual* (1), secretive (1), Slav (1), swear word (1), tolerant (1), uncultured (1), uncivilized* (1), understanding* (1), various (1), well-conducted and educated (1), well-read (1).
10. What are the person's emotions?	Emotional (30), cheerful (18), quick-tempered (14), restrained (14), stable (8), kind (7), open (6), calm (6), sincere (6), with an average level of emotions* (6), expressive (5), balanced (4), explosive* (4), impulsive (4), bright (3), liberated (3), unemotional (3), extrovert (2), energetic* (2), high (2), moderate* (2), persistent (2), passionate* (2), quiet* (2), romantic (2), self-confident (2), secretive (2), adaptive* (1), animate (1), animate* (1), any* (1), abrupt* (1), big (1), benevolent* (1), benevolent* (1), best (1), cool (1), controlled (1), crafty (1), confident (1), charismatic (1), cunning* (1), developed (1), enthusiastic (1), exuberant (1), empathic (1), frivolous (1), gentle (1), hard (1), high (1), high-quality (1), irritable (1), I don't know (1), intriguer (1), joyful (1), mature (1), multifaceted (1), not emotional (1), nothing occurs to me (1), optimist (1), open* (1), patient (1), persistent* (1), passionate (1), receptive (1), real (1), restless (1), strong-

<p>11. What is the person's appearance?</p>	<p>willed (1), sentimental (1), strong (1), sensual (1), sensitive (1), temperamental (1), unusual (1), unrestrained* (1), unrestrained (1), unbalanced (1), various (1), vulnerable (1), withdrawn* (1), wise (1). Attractive (55), beautiful* (40), pretty (20), enticing (11), pleasant* (10), sexy* (7), comely (5), cute* (3), charming (3), average* (2), brunette (2), bright* (2), interesting* (2), ordinary* (2), provocative* (2), unusual* (2), awesome* (1), any* (1), awkward (1), blonde* (1), bearded (1), brutal (1), beautiful (for me)* (1), cool* (1), childish face (1), crazy* (1), confident (1), charismatic* (1), common* (1), doesn't matter (1), deceitful* (1), extravagant* (1), European-looking girl (1), fashionable* (1), Italian* (1), juicy* (1), masculine type* (1), manly (1), manly* (1), on the make (1), mind-blowing* (1), normal (1), normal* (1), neat (1), outward* (1), pink* (1), quiet* (1), repulsive* (1), redhead* (1), skinny stature, low stature* (1), snobbish (1), splendid* (1), stunning* (1), standard* (1), strict (1), sexy (1), such (1), sophisticated* (1), swear word (1), swear word* (1), ugly* (1), which fits my human factors, life position, character* (1), well-groomed (1).</p>
<p>12. What is the person's self-esteem?</p>	<p>High (40), self-confident (29), adequate self-esteem (20), average (13), heightened self-esteem (11), normal self-esteem (11), self-confident (9), narcissistic (8), adequate (6), low (4), moderate (3), self-critical (3), self-respecting (3), unconfident (3), above average (2), honest (2), sufficient (2), perplexed (2), underappreciated (2), aggressive (1), arrogant (1), appreciated (1), balanced (1), bottom (1), confident enough (1), considerable self-esteem (1), critical (1), common (1), confident user (1), deflated (1), developed (1), different (1), hill (1), heightened (1), healthy (1), hesitation (1), inadequate (1), knows place (1), measured (1), meh (1), narcissist (1), not vain (1), not very critical (1), none (1), open (1), objective (1), puzzled (1), poor self-esteem (1), restrained (1), realistic (1), sometimes overstated self-esteem (1), self-accepting (1), sensible (1), self-sufficient (1), self-critical (1), stunning, stable (1), self-respecting (1), stable (1), unconfident (1), without feeling of his/ her own importance (1), weaselly (1).</p>
<p>13. What is the person's attitude to the opposite gender?</p>	<p>Interested (19), attentive (17), respectful (10), friendly (9), normal (8), playful (7), open (6), interesting (4), polite (4), reserved (4), tolerant (3), active (2), arrogant* (2), attractive (2), caring (2), courteous (2), cautious (2), calm (2), excellent (2), gentle (2), indifferent (2), interesting (2), kind (2), moderate (2), neutral (2), neat (2), ordinary (2), positive (2), pleasant (2), sociable (2), sympathetic (2), self-confident (2), adequate (1), accepting (1), arrogant (1), affectionate (1), assertive (1), approving (1), agreeable (1), balanced (1), charismatic (1), cunning (1), cold (1), curious (1), charming (1), courteous (1), courteous* (1), considers men to be different people and tries to build mutually beneficial relationships (1), does not often tell all the information (1), dismissive (1), does not give reasons to be jealous (1), disrespectful (1), direct (1), different (1), extroverted (1), easy to get on with (1), exciting (1), evaluating (1), flirting (1), friendly (1), friendly* (1), flirty (1), fiery (1), fair (1), free (1), gentle (1), gallant (1), good (1), gay (1), honest (1), it does not matter because I'm keen on my gender (1), interested (1), impressive (1), intimate (1), indulgent (1), knowing when to stop loving (1), loves (1), loyal (1), lickerous (1), manipulative (1), mysterious (1), not aggressive (1), not withdrawn (1), neutral (1), neutral* (1), none (1), observant (1), ordinary (1), practical (1), pleasant (1), passionate (1), persistent (1), responsive (1), resourceful (1), responsible (1), romantic (1), sweet (1), sociable (1), sharply negative (1), sexy (1), sexy* (1), seductive (1), supportive (1), tasty (1), tall (1), tries to please and entice away (1), uncompliant (1), unpredictable (1), unscrupulous (1), user (1), very partial to it (1), value (1), well-mannered (1), "??"(1).</p>
<p>15. Where does the person flirt?</p>	<p>Everywhere (46), in communication (15), not in public places (13), at home (13), in the street (10), in a bar (9), at work (8), in the company (7), at a club (6), in public places (5), in life (4), intimately (4), in underground (4), in social networks (4), in a café (4), in private (4), at a party (3), in ripe situations (3), in a public place (3), on vacation (3), where there is an opportunity (3), when meeting (3), at any time (2), in establishments (2), in any situation (2), in the behavior (2), in relations (2), with the husband (2), where it is appropriate (2), at places to meet (1), at the right time (1), at university (1), at holidays (1), at a festival (1), environment (1), in interaction (1), in actions (1), it does not matter (1), in the jungle (1), in a comfortable (1), in personal communication (1), in St. Petersburg (1), in everyday life (1), indoors (1), in conversation (1), in a restaurant (1), in transport (1), in secluded places (1), on the internet (1), on occasion (1), surrounded by (1), where the person is comfortable (1), when dancing (1), where it is profitable (1), where there is a response (1), where the person considers it to be appropriate (1).</p>
<p>16. Whom does the person flirt with?</p>	<p>With me (57), with girls (28), with everybody (16), with opposite gender (15), with a guy (13), with a man (7), with a sympathizer (7), with women (6), with a person (6), with someone who the person likes (5), with men (3), not with me (2), with a friend (2), with people (2), with him (2), with the other half (2), with the surrounding people (2), acquainted (1), doesn't show it (1), in all cases (1), in the street (1), I don't know (1), not yet (1), only with me (1), polygamous (1), when the person wants it (1), with classmates (1), with a prey (1), with female (1), with a feminine Italian (1), with a woman (1), with animals (1), with anybody the person wants (1), with coworkers (1), with lionesses (1), with a golden youth (1), with a husband (1), with male (1), with a boss (1), with her (1), with an ugly girl (1), with an object of adoration (1), with all girls (1), with acquaintances (1), with spectators (1), with many people (1), with a partner (1), with a potential partner (1), with attractive people (1), with a girlfriend (1), with a dog (1), with an interlocutor (1), with those who the person chooses (1), with those who he/ she like (1), with someone who is interesting (1), with successful people (1), with franklins (1), with a closet (1).</p>

17. How polite is the person?	Polite (78), average (21), very polite (13), well-mannered (7), averagely polite (5), gallant (4), tactful (4), tall (4), courteous (3), cultured (3), moderate (3), normal (3), polite enough (3), cad (2), gentleman (2), important (2), lovely (2), ordinary (2), adequate courtesy (1), attentive (1), above average (1), a little rough at times (1), affectionate (1), according to the situation (1), a little coarse (1), average (1), balanced (1), between a canned meat opener and a spaniel puppy (1), courteous by the circumstances (1), comfortable (1), cultured (1), common (1), charming (1), candid but well-mannered (1), delicate (1), decent (1), dignified (1), enough (1), extraordinary (1), extremely polite (1), fair (1), gentle (1), good (1), immoral (1), inconsiderate (1), insolent (1), impolite (1), moderately polite (1), maximum polite (1), not always polite (1), not very (1), not so good (1), normal (1), polite enough (1), pleasant (1), respectful (1), reserved (1), rude (1), smarmy (1), situational (1), strange (1), supportive (1), tolerable (1), tolerant (1), thoughtful (1), uncivil (1), 8 out of 10 (1), 9 out of 10 (1), 7 out of 10 (1), 4 out of 10 (1), 4 out of 5 (1), 6 out of 10 (1).
18. What is the person in showing sense of humor?	Funny (47), cheerful (31), witty (15), humorist (13), very funny (7), active (3), moderate (3), ridiculous (3), adequate (2), black (2), cheap (2), good joke (2), good sense of humor (2), likes joking (2), tall (2), playful (2), resourceful (2), sharp on the tongue (2), subtle sense of humor (2), sarcastic (2), 10 out of 10 (2), absurd (1), artistic (1), affiliate (1), angry (1), at haphazard (1), almost a comedian (1), a strange sense of humor (1), accepts jokes (1), clear (1), clown (1), candid (1), careful (1), charismatic (1), cruel (1), doesn't understand toilet humor (1), does not show (1), developed (1), delicate (1), erudite (1), easy-going (1), extraordinary (1), gallows humor (1), gloomy (1), great (1), good (1), good level of humor (1), honest (1), it would be good if my jokes truly amused her (1), it's delivered on time (1), intellectual (1), interesting (1), interesting* (1), in different ways (1), is sarcastic (1), Jim Carrie (1), masked (1), maximum (1), maximum openness (1), not decisive (1), not funny (1), no matter (1), neutral (1), nervous (1), none (1), Nurlan Saburov (1), non-funny (1), out of control (1), peculiar (1), positive (1), playful (1), sarcasm and sharpness of mind (1), sarcastic (1), satirical (1), sensible (1), severe (1), specific humor (1), stand-up subtle (1), smiling (1), sparkling (1), the soul of the company (1), too cheerful (1), teasing men or flirting (1), takes the initiative (1), veiled sharp (1), vulgar (1), with a sense of humor (1), weak (1).
20. What is the person in the expression of sexuality?	Sexy (45), passionate (27), active (12), hot (7), relaxed (7), open (6), gentle (5), reserved (5), assertive (4), attractive (4), candid (4), ordinary (4), very much (4), aggressive (3), sincere (3), with a fight (3), brutal (2), coarse (2), confident (2), desirable (2), exciting (2), flexible (2), irritating (2), persistent (2), smutty (2), absolute (1), asexual (1), attentive (1), amorous (1), average (1), awesome (1), beast (1), confused (1), charming (1), courageous (1), charismatic (1), calm (1), conscious (1), dominant (1), delicious (1), diverse (1), doesn't show any feelings yet (1), does not show much (1), direct (1), everyone wants her (1), excellent (1), experienced (1), free experimenter (1), experimenter (1), has an appetite (1), impulsive (1), I don't know (1), intrusive (1), juicy peach (1), like that (1), masculine (1), none (1), normal (1), not sexy (1), out of control (1), outgoing (1), playful (1), patient (1), passive (1), quivering (1), quick-shot (1), real (1), restless (1), smooth (1), slutty (1), sexy kitten (1), seductive (1), sensual (1), sensual* (1), sensitive (1), selfish (1), without abuse (1), worthy (1), wild (1).
22. What is the person in conflict?	Aggressive (19), calm (19), I'm trying to settle the conflict (14), reserved (10), non-conflict (8), quick-tempered (7), avoids it (4), honest (4), insistent (4), keeps silent (4), non-aggressive (4), adequate (3), defends the point of view (3), fights (3), gets angry (3), hysterics (3), jokes (3), stubborn (3), talks (3), tries to escape from conflict (3), a compromise (2), abrupt (2), bold (2), compromise (2), cunning (2), direct (2), flexible (2), interested in resolving the conflict (2), passive (2), quarrels (2), reasonably proves point or agrees that she was wrong (2), realistic (2), sincere (2), sincere* (2), soft (2), sensible (2), solves peacefully (2), smart (2), sufferer (2), violent (2), active (1), attentive (1), avoids (1), avoiding (1), attracts attention (1), adjusts others (1), but does not press (1), argues (1), bullish (1), causes the right reaction (1), constructive (1), courteous (1), doesn't throw plates (1), drinks (1), decisive (1), demonstrative (1), diplomatic (1), gets into a fight (1), goes all the way (1), goes to reconciliation (1), gives way (1), interesting (1), loves to bring to the forest (1), lies (1), loud (1), listens to the opponent without interrupting (1), then expresses the point of view (1), listener (1), not tough (1), objective (1), polite (1), proves point (1), plays (1), puts himself/ herself above others (1), quite argumentative (1), rides out (1), retreats (1), rough edges (1), rational (1), scolds (1), smooths (1), scandalous (1), settles by diplomacy (1), sensitive (1), tries not to be in the spotlight (1), tries to resolve the conflict peacefully (1), tolerant (1), warring (1), worthy (1), wise (1), watches (1).

Note. Words with an asterisk (groupmate*, interesting*, etc.) in the presented associative fields in the original research correspond to the feminine Russian words.

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